

TiO₂-catalyzed photo-decolorization of some dyes

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Abstract : UV-irradiated TiO₂-catalyzed photodegradation of the dyes, reactofix yellow ME7GL, reactofix red 3BFN 150% and reactofix supra red HBSL, has been studied. The kinetics has been followed spectrophotometrically at the wavelength of the maximum absorption, λ_{max} , of the dyes in the visible region. The rate of the reaction depends on [dye] and [O₂], and on [TiO₂] when its concentration is below 0.2 g L⁻¹. On increasing [TiO₂] beyond 0.2 g L⁻¹, the rate attains a limiting value. On increasing pH, the rate decreases only slightly. At 7.0 pH and 0.2 g L⁻¹ TiO₂, the photodegradation kinetics is in conformity with the following experimental rate law.

$$R_{\text{obs}} = k_0[\text{dye}] + k_2[\text{dye}][\text{O}_2] + \frac{k_3 K_1 K_2 [\text{dye}][\text{O}_2]}{(1 + K_1[\text{O}_2])(1 + K_2[\text{dye}])}$$

where the rate constants k_0 and k_2 are related to uncatalysed and k_3 to TiO₂-catalyzed pathways. The complete decolorization of the dye is achieved in about 20 min.

Keywords : TiO₂, photochemical degradation, kinetics, Reactofix Yellow ME7GL, Reactofix Red 3BFN 150%, Reactofix Supra Red HBSL.

Introduction

The widespread use of dyes in textile industry is the major cause of water pollution and this necessitates the development of techniques for removal/mineralization of dyes in textile industry waste water. In this regard, the use of semiconductor photocatalytic degradation in the treatment of dyes in textile industry water effluents is a promising technique due to its ability to completely decolorize the effluent and partially mineralize the dyes in a short reaction period¹. The mechanistic and other details are available in papers and reviews¹⁻⁷. TiO₂-catalyzed photochemical degradation of organic pollutants in general, and dyes, in particular, in waste water has been the subject of numerous studies¹⁻¹⁰. The organics are mineralized into H₂O and CO₂ without generating any harmful by-products. This technique has been employed for the photomineralization of a large number of dyes such as, reactofix navy blue 2GFN⁹, dyes in waste water¹⁰, methylene blue¹¹, SBB dye¹², squirillum cyanine¹³, hydro-

phobic dye¹⁴, azo dye¹⁵, reactive black 5¹⁶ etc.

This paper presents the kinetics results of the TiO₂-catalyzed photodegradation of the three dyes, viz. reactofix yellow ME7GL, reactofix red 3BFN 150% and reactofix supra red HBSL, which are widely used in textile industry. The electrochemical degradation of reactofix red 3BFN 150%¹⁷ and reactofix supra red HBSL¹⁸ and the photochemical degradation of the latter⁹ have also been studied.

Experimental

Dyes and their spectral characteristics :

The dyes were obtained from Jaysynth Dyechem Ltd., Worli, Mumbai as a gift sample. Their characteristics are given below.

(i) *Reactofix Yellow ME7GL* : C.I. Reactive yellow 185; 1,3-benzene disulfonic acid, 4-[[5-(amino-carbonyl)-1-ethyl-1,6-dihydro-2-hydroxy-4-methyl-6-oxo-3-

pyridinyl]azo]-6-[[4-chloro-6-[[4-[[2(sulfoxy)ethyl]sulfonyl]phenyl]amino]-1,3,5-triazin-2-yl]amino]-sodium salt; molecular formula : $C_{26}H_{26}ClN_9O_{15}S_4 \cdot xNa$.

(iii) *Reactofix Supra Red HBSL N* : 2,7-naphthalene disulfonic acid, 4,4'-[[(6-chloro-1,3,5-triazine-2,4-diy)]diiimino]bis[5-hydroxy-6-[[4-[[2-(sulfoxy)ethyl]-

(ii) *Reactofix Red 3BFN 150%* : C.I. Reactive red 195; 1,5-naphthalene disulfonic acid, 2-[[[8-[[4-chloro-6-[[3-[[2-(sulfoxy)ethyl]sulfonyl]phenyl]amino]-1,3,5-triazin-2-yl]-amino]-1-hydroxy-3,6-disulfo-2-naphthalenyl]azo]-penta-sodium salt; molecular formula : $C_{31}H_{24}ClN_7O_{19}S_6 \cdot 5Na$.

sulfonyl]phenyl]azo]-sodium salt; molecular formula : $C_{39}H_{32}ClN_9O_{26}S_8 \cdot xNa$.

The UV-Visible spectra of the dyes were recorded and the values of λ_{max} and molar extinction coefficients, ϵ , are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Values of λ_{max} and ϵ for dyes

Dye	λ_{max}	ϵ
Reactofix Yellow ME7GL	300, 421 nm	1.4×10^4 ($\lambda = 421$ nm)
Reactofix Red 3BFN 150%	283, 539 nm	2.4×10^4 ($\lambda = 539$ nm)
Reactofix Supra Red HBSL	290, 531 nm	3.0×10^4 ($\lambda = 531$ nm)

Kinetics procedure :

Solutions of dye and other chemicals were prepared in the double-distilled water. The photodegradation reactions were carried out in the immersion-well photochemical reactor (SAIC). The light source was a 6 W low pressure mercury vapor lamp, which emitted over 90% radiation at 254 nm. The reaction assembly was mounted on the magnetic stirrer. The dye solution of known concentration was filled in the reactor and weighed amount of TiO₂ (Lancaster Synthesis, 99% pure) was added. Since in photo-mineralization reactions the oxygen is the real oxidant, the O₂-N₂ gas mixture in desired gas ratio (0-100%) was passed through a T-tube, the head-ends of which were connected to O₂ and N₂-cylinders through rotameters, and the middle arm was connected to a Teflon tube through which the gas mixture was continuously passed in the reactor via a side opening. By adjusting the flow rates of N₂ and O₂, the desired composition of the N₂-O₂ mixture was achieved. There was another side opening in the reactor, which allowed the outflow of the gas mixture from the head space as well as withdrawal of reaction mixture through a Teflon tube. The D.O. meter (Thermo Orion 805 A+) probe was used for measuring the O₂ concentration. Before initiating the reaction, the gas mixture was allowed to pass for about fifteen minutes to achieve the equilibrium between the dissolved O₂, and the O₂ in the gas mixture. Thereafter, the degradation reaction was initiated by switching on the lamp.

During photolysis, the reaction suspension was continuously stirred magnetically to keep the catalyst, TiO₂, afloat. The aliquots were withdrawn periodically using a Teflon tube and syringe. After removing TiO₂ through centrifugation, absorbance measurements were made on a Hitachi U-2000 spectrophotometer. For comparison, the absorbance of the blank unirradiated solution was also measured in each case.

The rate measurements were generally reproducible within ±10%. All calculations were performed on MSExcel.

The lamp intensity was determined using uranyl oxalate actinometry and its value was found to be 1.9 × 10¹⁹ photon s⁻¹.

Determination of chemical oxygen demand (COD) :

The COD values were determined before, COD_{bf}, and after, COD_{af}, TiO₂-catalyzed photodegradation of the dyes using standard procedure. The values were as follows :

Reactofix Yellow (1.68 × 10⁻⁴ M), COD_{bf} = 160, COD_{af} = 80; Reactofix Red (1.32 × 10⁻⁴ M), COD_{bf} = 155, COD_{af} = 92; Reactofix Supra (1.11 × 10⁻⁴ M), COD_{bf} = 160, COD_{af} = 90.

Results and discussion

Uncatalyzed photodegradation of dyes :

Initially, the photodegradation of dyes was studied both in the absence and in the presence of O₂, but without using TiO₂ as catalyst. The uncatalyzed degradation kinetics was of first order in [dye], and the first order rate constants, *k*₁, were obtained from log [absorbance] versus time plots (Table 2). The kinetics was defined by eq. (1) in the presence of O₂, and by eq. (2) in the absence of O₂ in N₂ atmosphere.

$$-\frac{d[\text{dye}]}{dt} = [k_0 + k_2[\text{O}_2]][\text{dye}]$$

or

$$k_1 = k_0 + k_2[\text{O}_2] \tag{1}$$

$$-\frac{d[\text{dye}]}{dt} = k_0[\text{dye}] \tag{2}$$

where *k*₀ and *k*₂ are rate constants for [O₂]-independent and [O₂]-dependent dye decolorization paths, respectively in the absence of TiO₂. The value of *k*₀ and *k*₂ are collected in Table 3. TiO₂ displayed no catalysis in photodegradation of dyes in the absence of O₂ in an inert atmosphere (with N₂).

TiO₂-catalyzed decolorization :

Photocatalyzed-degradation was studied in the presence of O₂ by using N₂-O₂ mixtures in different proportions. The reaction displayed a first order in [dye] and the first order rate constants in presence of TiO₂, *k*₄ (Table 2), were obtained from log [absorbance] versus time plots. The photodegradation in the [TiO₂]-range, 0.04-0.2 g L⁻¹ was defined by rate law (3).

$$k_4 = k_1 + k_5[\text{TiO}_2] \tag{3}$$

where *k*₅ is the rate constant for TiO₂-catalyzed reactions. Beyond [TiO₂] ≥ 0.2 g L⁻¹, the reaction became independent of [TiO₂]. And the eq. (3) became eq. (4).

$$k_4 = k_1 + k_6 \tag{4}$$

where *k*₆ is the rate constant for catalyzed pathway, al-

Table 2. The values of the first order rate constants k_1 and k_4 for the photodegradation of dyes

[dye] (mol L ⁻¹)	[O ₂] (mol L ⁻¹)	pH	[TiO ₂] (g L ⁻¹)	k_1 (s ⁻¹)	k_4 (s ⁻¹)
Reactofix Yellow ME7GL					
1.68 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.0	6.7	-	1.2 × 10 ⁻⁵	-
1.68 × 10 ⁻⁴	5.48 × 10 ⁻⁴	6.7	-	2.8 × 10 ⁻⁵	-
1.68 × 10 ⁻⁴	10.95 × 10 ⁻⁴	6.7	-	5.7 × 10 ⁻⁵	-
1.68 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.0	6.7	0.20	1.5 × 10 ⁻⁵	-
11.2 × 10 ⁻⁵	10.95 × 10 ⁻⁴	6.7	0.20	-	2.8 × 10 ⁻³
16.8 × 10 ⁻⁵	10.95 × 10 ⁻⁴	6.7	0.20	-	2.2 × 10 ⁻³
16.8 × 10 ⁻⁵	8.21 × 10 ⁻⁴	6.7	0.20	-	2.0 × 10 ⁻³
16.8 × 10 ⁻⁵	5.48 × 10 ⁻⁴	6.7	0.20	-	1.8 × 10 ⁻³
16.8 × 10 ⁻⁵	2.74 × 10 ⁻⁴	6.7	0.20	-	1.3 × 10 ⁻³
22.4 × 10 ⁻⁵	10.95 × 10 ⁻⁴	6.7	0.20	-	1.7 × 10 ⁻³
1.68 × 10 ⁻⁴	10.95 × 10 ⁻⁴	4.0	0.20	-	3.0 × 10 ⁻³
1.68 × 10 ⁻⁴	10.95 × 10 ⁻⁴	6.0	0.20	-	2.3 × 10 ⁻³
1.68 × 10 ⁻⁴	10.95 × 10 ⁻⁴	8.0	0.20	-	2.1 × 10 ⁻³
Reactofix Red 3BFN 150%					
1.32 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.0	6.5	-	2.8 × 10 ⁻⁴	-
1.32 × 10 ⁻⁴	5.48 × 10 ⁻⁴	6.5	-	3.3 × 10 ⁻⁴	-
1.32 × 10 ⁻⁴	10.95 × 10 ⁻⁴	6.5	-	3.8 × 10 ⁻⁴	-
1.32 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.0	6.5	0.20	3.0 × 10 ⁻⁵	-
8.8 × 10 ⁻⁵	10.95 × 10 ⁻⁴	6.5	0.20	-	5.0 × 10 ⁻³
12.3 × 10 ⁻⁵	10.95 × 10 ⁻⁴	6.5	0.20	-	4.3 × 10 ⁻³
1.32 × 10 ⁻⁴	10.95 × 10 ⁻⁴	6.5	0.20	-	3.8 × 10 ⁻³
1.32 × 10 ⁻⁴	8.21 × 10 ⁻⁴	6.5	0.20	-	3.1 × 10 ⁻³
1.32 × 10 ⁻⁴	5.48 × 10 ⁻⁴	6.5	0.20	-	2.2 × 10 ⁻³
1.32 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.74 × 10 ⁻⁴	6.5	0.20	-	1.5 × 10 ⁻³
15.8 × 10 ⁻⁵	10.95 × 10 ⁻⁴	6.5	0.20	-	3.7 × 10 ⁻³
1.32 × 10 ⁻⁴	10.95 × 10 ⁻⁴	4.0	0.20	-	4.5 × 10 ⁻³
1.32 × 10 ⁻⁴	10.95 × 10 ⁻⁴	6.0	0.20	-	4.2 × 10 ⁻³
1.32 × 10 ⁻⁴	10.95 × 10 ⁻⁴	8.0	0.20	-	4.0 × 10 ⁻³
Reactofix Supra Red HBSL					
1.1 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.0	4.0	-	2.2 × 10 ⁻⁵	-
1.1 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.74 × 10 ⁻⁴	4.0	-	4.9 × 10 ⁻⁵	-
1.1 × 10 ⁻⁴	10.95 × 10 ⁻⁴	4.0	-	10.2 × 10 ⁻⁵	-
1.1 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.0	4.0	0.20	2.4 × 10 ⁻⁵	-
7.4 × 10 ⁻⁵	10.95 × 10 ⁻⁴	4.0	0.20	-	-
11.1 × 10 ⁻⁵	10.95 × 10 ⁻⁴	4.0	0.20	-	4.0 × 10 ⁻³
11.1 × 10 ⁻⁵	8.21 × 10 ⁻⁴	4.0	0.20	-	3.0 × 10 ⁻³
11.1 × 10 ⁻⁵	5.48 × 10 ⁻⁴	4.0	0.20	-	2.7 × 10 ⁻³
11.1 × 10 ⁻⁵	2.74 × 10 ⁻⁴	4.0	0.20	-	2.3 × 10 ⁻³
14.7 × 10 ⁻⁵	10.95 × 10 ⁻⁴	4.0	0.20	-	1.2 × 10 ⁻³
1.1 × 10 ⁻⁴	10.95 × 10 ⁻⁴	4.0	0.20	-	2.2 × 10 ⁻³
1.1 × 10 ⁻⁴	10.95 × 10 ⁻⁴	6.0	0.20	-	3.0 × 10 ⁻³
1.1 × 10 ⁻⁴	10.95 × 10 ⁻⁴	9.0	0.20	-	2.5 × 10 ⁻³
				-	2.0 × 10 ⁻³

Table 3. The values of k_0 , k_2 and K_1 for the uncatalyzed photodegradation of dyes

[dye]	k_0 (s ⁻¹)	k_2 (L mol s ⁻¹)	K_1
Reactofix Yellow ME7GL	1.5×10^{-5} (eq. 2)	4.2×10^{-2} (eq. 2)	3.1×10^3 (eq. 5)
	1.1×10^{-5} (eq. 1)		
Reactofix Red 3BFN 150%	2.8×10^{-4} (eq. 2)	9.5×10^{-2} (eq. 2)	1.0×10^3 (eq. 5)
	2.8×10^{-4} (eq. 1)		
Reactofix Supra Red HBSL	2.1×10^{-5} (eq. 2)	7.1×10^{-2} (eq. 2)	0.74×10^3 (eq. 5)
	2.5×10^{-5} (eq. 1)		

though independent of [TiO₂]. Thus, eq. (3) is applicable in limited [TiO₂]-range only. Subsequently, reaction kinetics was studied at 0.2 g L⁻¹ [TiO₂] at which eq. (4) was applicable.

On increasing [O₂], the values of k_4 is increased (Table 2). The plot of k_4 versus [O₂] gave an intercept corresponding to uncatalyzed [O₂]-independent reaction. For understanding the nature of the [O₂]-dependence of TiO₂-catalyzed pathway, k_6 , the values of k_1 and k_4 were determined at different [O₂]. Dependence of k_6 on [O₂] was defined by rate law (5).

$$k_6 = k_4 - k_1 = \frac{k_7 K_1 [O_2]}{1 + K_1 [O_2]} \quad (5)$$

where k_7 is [dye]-dependent rate constant and K_1 is adsorption equilibrium constant for O₂ on TiO₂ surface. According to eq. (5) the plot of $1/k_6$ versus $1/[O_2]$ was linear and from intercept and slope of these plots (Fig. 1), values of K_1 for dyes were obtained (Table 3). Simi-

Fig. 1. Dependence of the rate of photochemical degradation of dye on [O₂] in presence of TiO₂, at room temperature and at (1) [Reactofix Yellow ME7GL dye] = 1.68×10^{-4} mol L⁻¹ (pH = 6.7); (2) [Reactofix Yellow 3BFN 150% dye] = 1.68×10^{-4} mol L⁻¹ (pH = 6.5); (3) [Reactofix Supra Red HBSL dye] = 1.32×10^{-4} mol L⁻¹ (pH = 4.0).

lar K_1 values have been reported for chloroform (1.3×10^3)¹⁹, 4-chlorophenol (3.4×10^3)⁷, phenol (8.6×10^3)²⁰ and reactofix navy blue 2GFN (3.4×10^3)⁹.

An interesting feature of this study is the decrease in the values of k_4 and k_6 with increase in [dye] (Table 2). In all those TiO₂-catalyzed photogradation reactions in which this kind of behavior is observed, Langmuir adsorption isotherm, eq. (6) at a fixed [O₂] and pH has been applied to explain the results²⁰⁻²²

$$R_{\text{cat}} = \frac{-d[\text{dye}]}{dt} = k_6 [\text{dye}] = \frac{k_8 K_2 [\text{dye}]}{1 + K_2 [\text{dye}]} \quad (6)$$

where K_2 is the equilibrium constant for the adsorption of the dye on TiO₂ surface and k_8 is [O₂]-dependent rate constant.

Based on the treatment of Mathews^{21,22}, eq. (6) on integration and applying boundary conditions that when $t = 0$, [dye] = [dye]₀, we get eq. (7).

$$t = \left(\frac{1}{k_8 K_2} \right) \ln \left(\frac{[\text{dye}]_0}{[\text{dye}]} \right) + \frac{([\text{dye}]_0 - [\text{dye}])}{k_8} \quad (7)$$

where t is the time during which concentration of dye reduces from [dye]₀ to [dye]. From eq. (7), the half life period, $t_{1/2}$, is obtained as in the eq. (8).

$$t_{1/2} = \left(\frac{0.5[\text{dye}]_0}{k_8} \right) + \frac{0.693}{k_8 K_2} \quad (8)$$

The experimental value of $t_{1/2}$ was obtained from eq. (9).

$$t_{1/2} = 0.693/k_6 \quad (9)$$

The plots of $t_{1/2}$ versus [dye]₀, which are linear, are shown in Fig. 2. From the slopes and intercepts of these plots, the values of k_8 , $k_8 K_2$ and K_2 were obtained. These are collected in Table 4.

Fig. 2. The values of $t_{1/2}$ at $[\text{TiO}_2] = 0.2 \text{ g L}^{-1}$ and 100% O_2 for TiO_2 -catalyzed pathway at room temperature and at pH 7.0 : (1) [Reactofix Yellow ME7GL dye]; (2) [Reactofix Red 3BFN 150% dye]; (3) [Reactofix Supra Red HBSL dye].

where $k_7 = \frac{k_3 K_2 [\text{dye}]}{1 + K_2}$ and $k_8 = \frac{k_3 K_1 [\text{O}_2]}{1 + K_1 [\text{O}_2]}$. It

may be pointed out that k_0 , k_2 and k_3 are composite rate constants and k_3 includes dependence on intensity of light also.

The photocatalytic photodegradation of the dyes is possible by exposure to both visible or UV light. Whereas in the case of visible irradiation, the dye, and not the TiO_2 , is excited, in the case of UV-irradiation, the semiconductor is excited. The results of the UV-irradiated TiO_2 -catalyzed photodegradation of the dyes, S, can be explained by the mechanistic steps (12–20) as suggested previously⁷.

Table 4. The values of k_8 , K_2 and $k_8 K_2$ for the photodegradation of organic compounds

Organic compounds	k_8 ($\text{mol L}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$)	K_2 (mol L^{-1})	$k_8 K_2$ (s^{-1})	Reference
Methylene Blue	0.54×10^{-7}	2.58×10^4	0.00138	22
Salicylic acid	1.27×10^{-7}	1.4×10^4	0.00177	21
Phenol	0.77×10^{-7}	2.3×10^4	0.00178	21
Benzoic acid	1.12×10^{-7}	1.7×10^4	0.0019	21
2-Naphthol	0.91×10^{-7}	1.7×10^4	0.00155	21
Naphthalene	2.72×10^{-7}	1.07×10^4	0.0029	21
Fluorescein	0.7×10^{-7}	3.15×10^4	0.0022	21
Reactofix Yellow ME7GL	3.3×10^{-7}	2.74×10^4	0.009063	This work
Reactofix Red 3BFN 150%	4.8×10^{-7}	2.6×10^4	0.0124	This work
Reactofix Supra Red HBSL	2.8×10^{-7}	6.2×10^4	0.0173	This work
Reactofix Navy Blue	2.0×10^{-7}	4.66×10^5	0.093	9

A variation in pH (5–9) had only a small rate decreasing effect (Table 2) as noted previously by Mills *et al.*⁷.

On combining eqs. (4) and (6) the complete rate law for TiO_2 -catalyzed pathway becomes eq. (10).

$$R_{\text{cat}} = \frac{k_3 K_1 K_2 [\text{dye}] [\text{O}_2]}{(1 + K_1 [\text{O}_2]) (1 + K_2 [\text{dye}])} \quad (10)$$

On including the rate law (1) for uncatalyzed reaction, the complete rate law for photo-mineralization of dyes becomes eq. (11).

$$R_{\text{obs}} = k_0 [\text{dye}] + k_2 [\text{dye}] [\text{O}_2] + \frac{k_3 K_1 K_2 [\text{dye}] [\text{O}_2]}{(1 + K_1 [\text{O}_2]) (1 + K_2 [\text{dye}])} \quad (11)$$

In eq. (17), O_2 is thought to be non-competitively adsorbed onto the surface of the TiO_2 at Ti^{III} sites. The degradation of the dye generates intermediates, Q_i , which are further mineralized by reactions similar to eq. (19). The mechanistic sequence (12–20) is followed by other reactions involving the formation of H_2O and H_2O_2 .

In our case, the kinetics has been studied by measuring the change in absorbance in the visible region, resulting from the change in [dye] due to the degradation of the chromophoric groups. This would lead to the formation of several intermediates, which will absorb most likely in the UV-range. Thus the absorbance measurements most likely ignore the changes in the concentrations of intermediates. Keeping this in view, from the mechanism (12–20), the rate eq. (20) for TiO₂-catalyzed photodegradation of organic compounds can be derived.

$$-d[S]/dt = k_3 K_1 K_2 [S][O_2] / \{(1 + K_1 [O_2]) (1 + K_2 [S])\} \quad (21)$$

where k_3 is the composite rate constant for the photodegradation (steps 19–20), and K_1 is related to steps (16–17) and K_2 to step (18).

It is of interest to compare the relative reactivity of the three dyes investigated. Based on the values of k_0 and k_2 (Table 3), the rate of the uncatalyzed photodegradation follows the reactivity order : Reactofix Red 3BFN 150% > Reactofix Supra Red HBSL > Reactofix Yellow ME7GL. Whereas the photodegradation of the former in absence of O₂ is more than ten times faster than the latter two, the difference is not much-being within a factor of two – for oxygen dependent pathway.

The order in the values of K_2 is : Reactofix Supra Red HBSL > Reactofix Yellow ME7GL > Reactofix Red 3BFN 150%. A comparison of composite rate constant, $k_8 K_2$, values for TiO₂-catalyzed photodegradations shows the order of reactivity to be : Reactofix Supra Red HBSL ~ Reactofix Red 3BFN 150% > Reactofix Yellow ME7GL.

The values of rate parameters for several organic compounds are available from the literature and these are collected in Table 4. The values of K_2 and $k_8 K_2$ are seen to be of the same order of magnitude for different organic compounds. The values of the equilibrium constants (K_1) for the adsorption of O₂ on particle surface (Table 3) in all the cases are of the same order of magnitude, and this strongly supports the fact that the mechanism operating in our studies is same as proposed by other workers^{7,21,22}.

Conclusion :

Photocatalytic degradation studies carried out in this work using TiO₂/UV clearly establishes its utility in decolorization of the dye, which is accomplished readily in about 20 min. The degradation followed first order kinetics and could be fitted to Langmuir-Hinshelwood model.

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